

Post-COVID Performance and Resilience of the Casablanca Stock Exchange (2020–2025): A Comparative and Structural Analysis

Performance et résilience post-COVID de la Bourse de Casablanca (2020–2025): une analyse comparative et structurelle.

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Conflict of interest: The author reports no conflict of interest.

To quote this article: ZOUGARI .Y, & EL BAKKOUCHI .M (2026) «

Post-COVID Performance and Resilience of the Casablanca Stock Exchange (2020–2025): A Comparative and Structural Analysis »,

IJAME : Volume 02, N° 19 | Pp: 084 – 112.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.19166462

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Abstract

This study analyzes the post-COVID performance and resilience of the Casablanca Stock Exchange over the 2019–2024 period, with a focus on the macroeconomic determinants of stock market returns. Using annual data, the research combines descriptive analysis and a parsimonious Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model to examine the relationship between GDP growth and MASI annual returns. The results reveal significant fluctuations during the pandemic shock (2020), followed by a strong rebound (2021), an inflation-driven correction (2022), and a stabilization phase (2023–2024). The correlation and regression analyses indicate a positive association between economic growth and stock returns, although statistical significance is limited due to the small sample size. The findings suggest that real economic activity played a meaningful role in shaping stock market dynamics during the post-pandemic recovery. While the Moroccan equity market demonstrated cyclical resilience, it remains sensitive to macroeconomic volatility and monetary conditions. The study contributes to the limited empirical literature on frontier markets and highlights the importance of macro-financial linkages in understanding stock market behavior in emerging economies.

Keywords: *Post-COVID recovery; Casablanca Stock Exchange; MASI index; Economic growth; Stock market performance; Macroeconomic determinants; Frontier markets; OLS regression; Market resilience*

Résumé

Cette étude analyse la performance et la résilience post-COVID de la Bourse de Casablanca sur la période 2019–2024, en mettant l’accent sur les déterminants macroéconomiques des rendements boursiers. À partir de données annuelles, la recherche combine une analyse descriptive et un modèle de régression linéaire (OLS) parcimonieux afin d’examiner la relation entre la croissance du PIB et le rendement annuel du MASI. Les résultats mettent en évidence d’importantes fluctuations : choc en 2020, rebond marqué en 2021, correction liée à l’inflation en 2022, puis phase de stabilisation en 2023–2024. Les analyses de corrélation et de régression montrent une relation positive entre croissance économique et performance boursière, bien que la significativité statistique soit limitée en raison de la taille réduite de l’échantillon. Les conclusions suggèrent que l’activité économique réelle a joué un rôle déterminant dans la dynamique du marché actions durant la reprise post-pandémique. Le marché marocain a démontré une résilience cyclique, tout en restant sensible à la volatilité macroéconomique et aux conditions monétaires. Cette recherche contribue à la littérature empirique sur les marchés frontières et met en lumière l’importance des interactions macro-financières dans l’analyse des marchés émergents.

Mots-clés : *Reprise post-COVID ; Bourse de Casablanca ; Indice MASI ; Croissance économique ; Performance boursière ; Déterminants macroéconomiques ; Marchés frontières ; Régression OLS ; Résilience financière*

I. INTRODUCTION

Financial markets occupy a central position in modern economic systems because they facilitate the allocation of capital from surplus units to deficit units. By channeling savings toward productive investment opportunities, stock exchanges contribute to capital formation, technological upgrading, and long-term growth. In this sense, financial markets are not merely venues for trading securities; they are institutional mechanisms that enhance resource allocation efficiency and support macroeconomic stability.

The theoretical link between financial development and economic growth has been extensively examined in the literature. Ross Levine (1997) argues that well-functioning financial systems improve capital allocation, foster corporate governance, and reduce information asymmetries, thereby stimulating economic performance. Similarly, Robert G. King and Ross Levine (1993) provide empirical evidence that financial development is strongly associated with long-term growth across countries. These contributions suggest that stock markets play a catalytic role in mobilizing savings, diversifying risk, and facilitating investment decisions.

From a microeconomic perspective, financial markets enhance efficiency through price discovery and liquidity provision. According to Eugene F. Fama (1970), security prices reflect available information, enabling investors to make informed decisions. This informational function reduces uncertainty and improves the allocation of capital toward firms with stronger fundamentals. Moreover, liquid markets lower transaction costs and enable investors to adjust portfolios rapidly in response to changing macroeconomic conditions.

In emerging and frontier economies, the developmental role of stock exchanges becomes even more pronounced. These markets often complement banking systems by offering alternative sources of financing, particularly for large corporations and infrastructure projects. However, their effectiveness depends on institutional quality, regulatory oversight, and macroeconomic stability. Consequently, assessing the interaction between financial markets and economic performance is essential for understanding the broader development trajectory of countries such as Morocco.

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020 generated one of the most abrupt and synchronized global economic contractions in modern history. Financial markets reacted immediately to the uncertainty surrounding public health measures, supply chain disruptions, and the collapse in aggregate demand. Stock exchanges across advanced and emerging economies experienced sharp declines, heightened volatility, and unprecedented liquidity

pressures during the first quarter of 2020. This episode constitutes a natural experiment for examining market resilience under systemic stress.

From a macro-financial perspective, the pandemic shock differed from previous crises because it originated outside the financial system. Unlike the 2008 global financial crisis, which emerged from structural weaknesses within banking systems, COVID-19 represented an exogenous health shock that rapidly translated into economic and financial instability. According to the International Monetary Fund (2020), global output contracted sharply in 2020, triggering synchronized downturns across both developed and developing economies. Financial markets internalized expectations of declining corporate earnings, increased default risk, and prolonged uncertainty.

The volatility spike observed in global equity markets during March 2020 reflects what Robert J. Shiller (2003) describes as the amplification of investor sentiment during periods of heightened uncertainty. Behavioral responses such as panic selling, herding behavior, and overreaction to negative news intensified price fluctuations. At the same time, unprecedented monetary interventions by central banks—including interest rate cuts, liquidity injections, and asset purchase programs—played a stabilizing role in financial markets.

Emerging and frontier markets faced additional vulnerabilities during this period. Capital outflows, exchange rate pressures, and limited fiscal space constrained policy responses. Consequently, the pandemic exposed structural fragilities while also testing the institutional strength and adaptive capacity of domestic stock exchanges. Understanding how individual markets responded to this shock is essential for evaluating their resilience and long-term development prospects. In this context, the Moroccan stock market provides an instructive case for analyzing post-pandemic recovery dynamics within a frontier market framework.

The Casablanca Stock Exchange represents one of the most established capital markets in North Africa and plays a strategic role in Morocco's financial architecture. As a centralized marketplace for equity and debt securities, it contributes to corporate financing, portfolio diversification, and the broader modernization of the national financial system. Its evolution over the past two decades reflects Morocco's gradual integration into global capital markets and its efforts to strengthen financial governance and regulatory transparency.

Institutionally, the Moroccan capital market operates under the supervision of the Autorité Marocaine du Marché des Capitaux (AMMC), which ensures compliance, investor protection, and market integrity. This regulatory framework has progressively aligned with international standards, enhancing disclosure requirements and improving market surveillance mechanisms.

Such institutional strengthening is particularly relevant in periods of systemic stress, when investor confidence becomes a decisive factor for market stability.

Structurally, however, the Moroccan stock market exhibits characteristics typical of frontier markets. Market capitalization remains concentrated in a limited number of large firms, particularly in the banking, telecommunications, and industrial sectors. Liquidity levels are moderate compared to larger emerging markets, and trading activity may be sensitive to shifts in domestic macroeconomic conditions. These features make the market both vulnerable to external shocks and potentially responsive to domestic recovery dynamics.

The COVID-19 crisis therefore constituted a critical test for the resilience of the Moroccan capital market. The sharp contraction in 2020 was followed by phases of recovery, correction, and stabilization, reflecting the interaction between real economic conditions and investor expectations. The performance of the MASI index during this period offers insight into how quickly financial prices incorporated macroeconomic signals and policy interventions.

Moreover, the post-pandemic context has reopened discussions regarding market deepening, diversification of listed companies, digitalization of trading systems, and the attraction of institutional investors. The ability of the Casablanca Stock Exchange to strengthen its structural foundations will determine whether it can move from cyclical recovery toward sustainable long-term development. Consequently, analyzing its performance between 2019 and 2024 provides not only a short-term assessment of crisis resilience but also a broader evaluation of its structural trajectory within Morocco's economic development strategy.

Despite the growing body of literature examining the financial consequences of the COVID-19 crisis, empirical evidence remains unevenly distributed across regions and market classifications. Most studies have focused on advanced economies or large emerging markets, leaving frontier markets comparatively underexplored. Yet, frontier markets present distinct structural characteristics—lower liquidity, higher concentration ratios, and greater sensitivity to external shocks—that justify dedicated empirical investigation.

Early empirical analyses documented the immediate global stock market reaction to the pandemic. For instance, Ali M. Al-Awadhi et al. (2020) show that COVID-19 case growth significantly affected stock returns in China, while Zaremba, Adam et al. (2020) find that government intervention policies influenced market volatility across countries. Similarly, Ashraf, Badar Nadeem (2020) provides cross-country evidence that stock markets reacted negatively to the increase in confirmed cases, particularly during the early stages of the pandemic.

However, the majority of these contributions rely on high-frequency data from developed or major emerging markets. There is limited econometric evidence concerning North African markets and even less regarding Morocco specifically. While descriptive reports from regulatory authorities such as the Autorité Marocaine du Marché des Capitaux provide valuable statistical insights, peer-reviewed econometric analyses of the post-COVID performance of the Casablanca Stock Exchange remain scarce.

Furthermore, much of the existing literature emphasizes short-term volatility effects rather than medium-term resilience and structural recovery. The distinction between immediate shock absorption and sustained recovery is critical, particularly in frontier markets where financial depth and institutional capacity may influence adjustment speed. As noted by Didier, Tatiana et al. (2021), the recovery dynamics of financial markets differ substantially across countries depending on macroeconomic fundamentals and policy responses.

Therefore, a focused econometric assessment of the Moroccan stock market during the 2019–2024 period contributes to filling this gap by examining:

- (1) the relationship between macroeconomic conditions and stock returns, and
- (2) the degree of market resilience following the COVID-19 shock.

By combining descriptive and econometric analysis within a frontier market context, this study extends the existing literature beyond large-market evidence and provides new insights into the structural behavior of the Moroccan capital market.

The primary objective of this study is to assess the post-COVID performance and resilience of the Casablanca Stock Exchange over the 2019–2024 period. More specifically, the paper seeks to examine the extent to which macroeconomic fundamentals influenced stock market returns during and after the pandemic shock. By focusing on annual MASI returns as the main performance indicator, the study aims to identify whether economic growth dynamics were significantly associated with variations in market performance.

A second objective is to evaluate the degree of market resilience following the 2020 contraction. Financial resilience can be defined as the ability of a market to absorb shocks, stabilize, and return to a growth trajectory within a reasonable time horizon (Brunnermeier, 2009). In the Moroccan context, assessing resilience requires examining the speed of recovery in stock returns relative to macroeconomic normalization. The comparative analysis between contraction (2020), rebound (2021), correction (2022), and stabilization (2023–2024) provides a structured framework for evaluating this adjustment process.

Third, the study aims to contribute to the literature on macro-financial linkages in frontier markets. While theoretical models such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model (Sharpe, 1964) and the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (Ross, 1976) highlight the role of systematic and macroeconomic factors in asset pricing, empirical validation remains context-specific. By testing the relationship between GDP growth and MASI returns within a parsimonious regression framework, this research offers evidence grounded in Moroccan data.

Finally, the paper seeks to provide policy-relevant insights for regulators and market participants. Understanding the sensitivity of stock performance to macroeconomic fluctuations may inform monetary policy coordination, regulatory reforms, and market development strategies. In this regard, the study bridges academic analysis and practical financial governance considerations, positioning the Moroccan capital market within a broader post-pandemic economic transformation process.

This article is structured according to the conventional IMRAD framework in order to ensure methodological clarity and analytical coherence. Following the introductory section, the second section develops the theoretical foundations and reviews the relevant literature on financial market efficiency, risk–return theories, macroeconomic determinants of stock performance, and crisis-related behavioral dynamics. This section establishes the conceptual basis for examining the relationship between macroeconomic conditions and stock market performance in a frontier market context.

The third section formulates the research problem, presents the research questions, and states the main hypothesis guiding the empirical investigation. Particular attention is given to clarifying the theoretical rationale underlying the expected positive relationship between economic growth and stock returns, as suggested by financial development theory and macro-financial linkage literature (King & Levine, 1993; Levine, 1997).

The fourth section outlines the methodological approach. It describes the research design, data sources, variable construction, and econometric specification. A parsimonious ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model is adopted to ensure statistical validity given the limited time series length. The section also explains the descriptive statistical procedures and the rationale for model selection.

The fifth section presents the empirical results. It begins with a descriptive analysis of the evolution of MASI returns and GDP growth between 2019 and 2024, followed by correlation analysis and regression estimation. The findings are then interpreted in light of theoretical

expectations and the broader literature on crisis resilience and macroeconomic sensitivity of stock markets.

The final section concludes the paper by summarizing the main results, discussing theoretical and policy implications, acknowledging methodological limitations, and proposing directions for future research on the development trajectory of the Moroccan capital market.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Market efficiency and information integration

The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) constitutes one of the foundational pillars of modern financial economics. Initially formalized by Eugene F. Fama (1970), the theory posits that asset prices fully and instantaneously reflect all available information. Under this framework, securities are fairly priced at every point in time, and abnormal returns cannot be systematically achieved through publicly available information. The EMH distinguishes between three forms of market efficiency: weak, semi-strong, and strong, depending on the information set incorporated into prices.

In its weak form, current prices reflect all past price information, implying that technical analysis cannot consistently generate excess returns. The semi-strong form asserts that prices adjust rapidly to all publicly available information, including macroeconomic announcements, earnings reports, and policy decisions. The strong form extends this proposition to private information, suggesting that even insiders cannot systematically outperform the market. Empirical research has largely supported weak-form efficiency in developed markets, though evidence is more mixed for emerging and frontier markets (Fama, 1991).

The theoretical implications of EMH are particularly relevant in crisis contexts. During periods of systemic shocks, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, financial markets are expected to incorporate new information—ranging from infection rates to fiscal stimulus announcements—into prices without persistent inefficiencies. However, the speed and completeness of this adjustment may vary across markets depending on liquidity, institutional quality, and investor composition. Frontier markets may exhibit slower information diffusion due to lower trading volumes and limited analyst coverage.

The post-pandemic trajectory of stock markets provides an empirical setting to evaluate semi-strong efficiency. If macroeconomic recovery signals—such as GDP growth rebound—are quickly reflected in stock returns, this would support the informational efficiency of the market.

Conversely, delayed adjustments or excessive volatility may indicate temporary deviations from efficiency, potentially influenced by behavioral factors (Shiller, 2003).

Subsequent refinements of EMH emphasize that market efficiency should be interpreted as a joint hypothesis involving both market rationality and the validity of the asset-pricing model used for testing (Fama, 1991). Moreover, empirical anomalies—such as excess volatility or momentum effects—have led scholars to reconsider the strict form of efficiency, particularly in less mature financial systems (Lo, 2004). These debates highlight the importance of contextual empirical evaluation rather than assuming universal efficiency.

In the case of the Casablanca Stock Exchange, assessing whether stock returns co-move with macroeconomic fundamentals in the post-COVID period provides indirect evidence regarding the degree of informational efficiency. The regression analysis conducted in this study therefore contributes to evaluating semi-strong efficiency within a frontier market framework.

The Random Walk Hypothesis (RWH) is closely related to the Efficient Market Hypothesis and asserts that successive price changes in financial markets are independent and identically distributed. The core implication is that future price movements cannot be predicted based on past price information. Early empirical support for this proposition was provided by Maurice G. Kendall (1953), who observed that stock price series exhibited no systematic patterns and appeared to follow a random trajectory. This finding challenged earlier beliefs that markets moved in discernible cycles or trends.

The formalization of the random walk model in finance is often attributed to Paul A. Samuelson (1965), who demonstrated that if markets are informationally efficient, price changes must follow a martingale process. In such a framework, only new and unpredictable information can generate price movements. Because new information is, by definition, random, price changes should also appear random. This theoretical linkage establishes the Random Walk Hypothesis as a statistical manifestation of weak-form market efficiency.

Empirical research testing the random walk behavior of stock prices has employed variance ratio tests, autocorrelation analysis, and unit root tests. Andrew W. Lo and A. Craig MacKinlay (1988) developed variance ratio tests that challenged the strict random walk assumption in certain markets, identifying short-term return dependencies. Such findings suggest that while markets may be broadly efficient, deviations from pure randomness can occur, especially in less mature financial systems.

In emerging and frontier markets, evidence regarding random walk behavior is mixed. Lower liquidity, limited market depth, and higher transaction costs may lead to serial correlations in

returns. These structural features can produce temporary predictability, particularly during periods of crisis when market sentiment and liquidity constraints amplify price movements.

The COVID-19 episode offers an empirical context in which the Random Walk Hypothesis can be indirectly assessed. If the Moroccan stock market rapidly incorporated pandemic-related news into prices without persistent serial dependence, this would support weak-form efficiency. Conversely, sustained return autocorrelation or excessive volatility clustering would indicate deviations from strict random walk dynamics.

Within this study, although the limited annual dataset restricts formal time-series testing of random walk properties, the theoretical framework remains relevant. The observed co-movement between macroeconomic recovery and stock returns provides indirect insight into whether price adjustments reflected new information efficiently or whether deviations from randomness were present in the post-pandemic adjustment process.

2.2. Risk and return theories

Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT), introduced by Harry M. Markowitz (1952), fundamentally transformed the analysis of investment decisions by formalizing the trade-off between risk and return. Markowitz demonstrated that rational investors should not evaluate securities in isolation but rather consider how each asset contributes to the overall risk and expected return of a portfolio. The central insight of the model is that diversification reduces unsystematic risk through imperfect correlations among assets.

In the mean–variance framework, investors aim to maximize expected return for a given level of risk or minimize risk for a given expected return. Risk is measured by the variance (or standard deviation) of portfolio returns, while expected return is defined as the weighted average of individual asset returns. The efficient frontier represents the set of optimal portfolios offering the highest expected return for each level of risk. Portfolios lying below the frontier are considered inefficient because a better risk–return combination is available.

A key implication of Portfolio Theory is that diversification benefits depend on the covariance structure between assets. When asset returns are imperfectly correlated, combining them can reduce overall portfolio volatility without proportionally reducing expected return. This principle is particularly relevant in periods of crisis, when correlations between assets may increase and diversification benefits decline. The COVID-19 shock highlighted how systemic risk can temporarily weaken diversification strategies, especially in markets characterized by sectoral concentration.

Subsequent extensions of Markowitz's framework integrated risk-free assets and led to the development of the Capital Market Line and the Capital Asset Pricing Model (Sharpe, 1964; Tobin, 1958). These developments reinforced the central role of systematic risk in determining expected returns. However, the foundational contribution of Markowitz remains the formal quantification of portfolio optimization under uncertainty.

In the context of the Moroccan stock market, Portfolio Theory provides a useful interpretative lens for understanding investor behavior during and after the pandemic. The significant fluctuations in MASI returns between 2020 and 2024 likely altered perceived risk–return trade-offs, influencing asset allocation decisions. Moreover, the relatively concentrated structure of the Casablanca Stock Exchange may limit diversification opportunities, amplifying the sensitivity of portfolio performance to macroeconomic shocks. Consequently, evaluating post-COVID performance also entails examining how risk perceptions and return expectations evolved within a constrained market structure.

The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), developed independently by William F. Sharpe (1964), John Lintner (1965), and Jan Mossin (1966), extends Modern Portfolio Theory by establishing a formal relationship between expected return and systematic risk. The central proposition of the CAPM is that the expected return of an asset depends solely on its exposure to market risk, measured by the beta coefficient (β). In equilibrium, investors are compensated only for bearing systematic risk, as unsystematic risk can be eliminated through diversification. The model is derived under assumptions of mean–variance optimization, homogeneous expectations, frictionless markets, and the existence of a risk-free asset. Under these conditions, all investors hold a combination of the risk-free asset and the market portfolio. The expected return of asset i is expressed as:

$$E(R_i) = R_f + \beta_i(E(R_m) - R_f)$$

where R_f represents the risk-free rate, $E(R_m)$ the expected market return, and β_i the sensitivity of asset i to market movements. The beta coefficient captures systematic risk and reflects the asset's covariance with the market portfolio relative to total market variance.

Empirical testing of the CAPM has generated extensive debate. Eugene F. Fama and Kenneth R. French (1992) found that beta alone does not fully explain cross-sectional differences in average stock returns, leading to the development of multifactor models. Nevertheless, the CAPM remains a benchmark framework for understanding the risk–return relationship and for interpreting how macroeconomic shocks may influence market performance.

In the context of the COVID-19 crisis, the CAPM provides a conceptual basis for understanding how changes in perceived market risk affect expected returns. A rise in macroeconomic uncertainty increases the equity risk premium, potentially leading to higher required returns and downward pressure on stock prices. Furthermore, variations in the policy interest rate—controlled by the Bank Al-Maghrib—influence the risk-free rate component of the CAPM equation, thereby affecting asset valuation.

Although the present study does not estimate beta coefficients at the firm level due to data limitations, the CAPM framework informs the interpretation of aggregate market movements. Changes in MASI returns may reflect adjustments in systematic risk perceptions linked to macroeconomic growth dynamics. Thus, the CAPM serves as a theoretical bridge between macroeconomic conditions and observed stock market performance in the Moroccan frontier market environment.

The Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT), developed by Stephen A. Ross (1976), emerged as an alternative to the Capital Asset Pricing Model by relaxing several of its restrictive assumptions. Unlike the CAPM, which relies on a single systematic risk factor represented by the market portfolio, the APT proposes that asset returns are generated by multiple macroeconomic factors. The model is grounded in the principle of arbitrage: in well-functioning financial markets, mispriced assets will be corrected through arbitrage trading, restoring equilibrium.

Formally, the expected return of asset i under the APT can be expressed as:

$$E(R_i) = R_f + \beta_{i1}F_1 + \beta_{i2}F_2 + \dots + \beta_{ik}F_k$$

where R_f is the risk-free rate, F_k represents systematic risk factors, and β_{ik} measures the sensitivity of asset i to each factor. Unlike the CAPM, the APT does not specify the exact identity of the risk factors; these are typically determined empirically and often include macroeconomic variables such as inflation, industrial production, interest rates, and GDP growth.

Empirical work has demonstrated that macroeconomic variables significantly influence stock returns. Nai-Fu Chen, Richard Roll, and Stephen A. Ross (1986) provide evidence that innovations in industrial production, inflation, and term structure variables are priced risk factors in U.S. stock returns. Their findings reinforce the theoretical proposition that asset pricing is sensitive to broader economic conditions rather than to a single market factor.

The flexibility of the APT framework makes it particularly suitable for analyzing stock markets in emerging and frontier economies. In such contexts, macroeconomic shocks may have amplified effects due to structural constraints, limited diversification, and stronger transmission

channels between real and financial sectors. During the COVID-19 period, fluctuations in GDP growth, inflation, and monetary policy likely acted as systematic risk factors influencing aggregate stock returns.

In the case of the Casablanca Stock Exchange, the APT provides a relevant theoretical foundation for examining the relationship between MASI returns and macroeconomic variables. Although the present study adopts a parsimonious regression model due to data limitations, the conceptual approach remains aligned with the multifactor logic of the APT. The selected macroeconomic variable—GDP growth—can be interpreted as a proxy for systematic economic risk influencing market performance during the post-pandemic adjustment period.

2.3. Macroeconomic determinants of stock market performance

The relationship between macroeconomic fundamentals and stock market performance constitutes a central theme in financial economics. Asset pricing models increasingly recognize that stock returns are influenced not only by firm-specific characteristics but also by broader economic conditions. Macroeconomic variables affect expected cash flows, discount rates, and risk premia, thereby shaping equity valuation dynamics. In this perspective, stock markets function as forward-looking indicators that incorporate expectations about real economic activity, price stability, and monetary conditions.

Empirical literature has documented strong linkages between macroeconomic fluctuations and stock returns across countries. Nai-Fu Chen, Richard Roll, and Stephen A. Ross (1986) demonstrate that innovations in macroeconomic variables significantly influence asset returns. Similarly, John Y. Campbell (1991) shows that expected returns vary over time in response to changes in economic conditions. These findings support the multifactor view of asset pricing and justify the examination of macroeconomic determinants in frontier markets such as Morocco.

Within the post-COVID context, macroeconomic variables gained renewed importance. Economic contraction, inflationary pressures, and monetary tightening episodes have directly influenced market expectations. Consequently, understanding the Moroccan stock market's trajectory requires a structured examination of economic growth, inflation, and interest rates as core determinants of performance.

Economic growth reflects the overall expansion of productive activity and corporate profitability within an economy. Higher GDP growth typically signals improved earnings prospects for listed firms, which should translate into higher stock valuations. From a theoretical standpoint, financial development and economic growth are mutually reinforcing

processes (King & Levine, 1993; Levine, 1997). Expanding output increases investment opportunities, enhances firm performance, and strengthens investor confidence.

Empirical evidence suggests that stock markets often anticipate economic cycles. Eugene F. Fama (1990) finds that stock returns are related to future real economic activity, supporting the view that financial markets incorporate growth expectations. Similarly, G. William Schwert (1990) highlights the interaction between macroeconomic volatility and stock return behavior. In emerging and frontier markets, the growth–returns relationship may be more pronounced due to stronger dependence on domestic economic conditions. In the Moroccan context, fluctuations in GDP growth during 2020–2024 likely influenced aggregate corporate earnings and investor sentiment. Therefore, testing the relationship between GDP growth and MASI returns provides insight into the macro-financial transmission mechanism in the post-pandemic period.

Inflation affects stock markets through multiple channels. First, rising inflation may reduce real returns by eroding purchasing power. Second, it can increase uncertainty regarding future monetary policy and discount rates. Theoretical debate persists regarding whether equities serve as a hedge against inflation. Irving Fisher (1930) proposed that nominal returns should adjust to expected inflation, implying a neutral long-term effect. However, empirical studies often document a negative relationship between inflation and stock returns.

For instance, Eugene F. Fama and G. William Schwert (1977) show that stock returns are negatively correlated with inflation, particularly when inflation is unexpected. Laurence B. Geske and Richard Roll (1983) argue that the negative relationship may reflect monetary policy responses and economic contraction effects rather than direct inflation impact.

During the post-COVID period, many economies—including Morocco—experienced temporary inflation surges driven by supply chain disruptions and energy price shocks. Such inflationary episodes may increase required returns and reduce present valuations, thereby exerting downward pressure on stock prices. Consequently, inflation dynamics constitute a relevant contextual variable in assessing post-pandemic market performance.

Interest rates represent a key transmission channel between monetary policy and financial markets. Through the discount rate mechanism, higher interest rates increase the present value denominator applied to future cash flows, reducing equity valuations. Conversely, lower rates stimulate investment and encourage portfolio reallocation toward riskier assets.

The theoretical linkage between interest rates and stock returns is well established. Franco Modigliani and Merton H. Miller (1958) emphasize the importance of capital structure and cost

of capital in corporate valuation. Additionally, John Y. Campbell and Robert J. Shiller (1988) show that changes in interest rates are associated with variations in stock prices and dividend yields. In practice, central bank policy rates influence investor asset allocation decisions. When monetary authorities tighten policy, fixed-income instruments become more attractive relative to equities, potentially triggering capital reallocation. In Morocco, adjustments in the policy rate by the Bank Al-Maghrib during 2022–2023 may have contributed to valuation corrections observed in the equity market. Overall, economic growth, inflation, and interest rates form an interconnected macroeconomic framework influencing stock market dynamics. While the present study adopts a parsimonious regression model due to data constraints, these macroeconomic variables provide essential theoretical grounding for interpreting post-COVID market performance in the Moroccan context.

2.4. Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework of this study is grounded in multifactor asset pricing theory and macro-financial linkage literature. Building on the Efficient Market Hypothesis (Fama, 1970), the Capital Asset Pricing Model (Sharpe, 1964), and the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (Ross, 1976), the model assumes that aggregate stock market performance reflects the integration of macroeconomic information into asset prices. In this perspective, stock returns respond to systematic economic factors that influence expected cash flows and discount rates.

Given the limited number of annual observations (2019–2024), the empirical specification adopts a parsimonious structure to preserve statistical validity. While several macroeconomic variables are theoretically relevant, only one core explanatory variable is retained for regression analysis. Additional macroeconomic indicators are incorporated descriptively to contextualize market dynamics without compromising econometric robustness.

The conceptual logic of the study can therefore be summarized as follows:

Macroeconomic conditions → Expectations of corporate profitability and risk → Stock market returns (MASI)

This structure aligns with prior evidence showing that stock returns are linked to real economic activity (Fama, 1990; Chen et al., 1986).

The primary dependent variable is the annual return of the MASI index, which represents the aggregate performance of the Moroccan equity market. The MASI (Moroccan All Shares Index) captures price movements of listed companies and serves as the benchmark indicator of market valuation at the Casablanca Stock Exchange.

Stock returns are widely used in empirical finance as a proxy for market performance because they reflect changes in investor expectations regarding future dividends, earnings growth, and macroeconomic conditions. According to Eugene F. Fama (1990), stock returns contain information about future real activity, reinforcing their suitability as an aggregate performance measure.

Formally, the annual return is calculated as:

$$R_t = \frac{P_t - P_{t-1}}{P_{t-1}}$$

where P_t denotes the index value at the end of year t . This measure captures the percentage variation in market valuation and serves as the dependent variable in the regression model.

The independent variable retained for econometric estimation is annual GDP growth rate. Economic growth reflects the expansion of aggregate output and corporate earnings potential. The theoretical justification for this choice is rooted in financial development theory, which posits that stock market performance is closely linked to real economic activity (King & Levine, 1993; Levine, 1997).

Empirical research confirms that stock markets often anticipate economic cycles. Eugene F. Fama (1990) documents a positive association between stock returns and future real output growth. GDP growth thus serves as a proxy for systematic economic risk and expected profitability conditions affecting listed firms.

Given the small sample size, retaining a single explanatory variable ensures model parsimony and avoids overfitting. The regression model is therefore specified as:

$$MASI_t = \alpha + \beta GDP_t + \varepsilon_t$$

where GDP_t represents annual economic growth.

Although not included in the regression model due to degrees-of-freedom constraints, several macroeconomic variables are examined descriptively to enrich the interpretation of market dynamics:

Inflation rate, which may affect real returns and discount rates (Fama & Schwert, 1977).

Policy interest rate, determined by the Bank Al-Maghrib, influencing capital allocation and valuation.

Market liquidity (trading volume and turnover ratio), reflecting market depth and resilience.

Volatility, capturing risk perception and uncertainty levels.

These variables are theoretically consistent with multifactor asset pricing models (Chen et al., 1986) but are treated descriptively in this study to maintain econometric rigor. Their inclusion

in the narrative analysis allows for a broader interpretation of post-COVID market behavior without compromising statistical validity.

III. RESEARCH PROBLEM AND HYPOTHESES

The COVID-19 pandemic generated an unprecedented macro-financial shock that disrupted economic activity and capital markets worldwide. While extensive empirical research has examined the reaction of developed and major emerging markets, considerably less attention has been devoted to frontier markets. In such markets, structural characteristics—limited liquidity, sectoral concentration, and stronger dependence on domestic economic cycles—may amplify the transmission of macroeconomic shocks to stock prices.

The Moroccan case is particularly relevant in this regard. The Casablanca Stock Exchange experienced a contraction in 2020, followed by phases of recovery, correction, and stabilization between 2021 and 2024. However, the extent to which these fluctuations reflect macroeconomic fundamentals rather than purely financial or behavioral dynamics remains insufficiently explored in the academic literature. Theoretically, asset pricing models suggest that stock returns should respond to systematic economic factors. According to Eugene F. Fama (1990), stock returns are linked to real economic activity, while Nai-Fu Chen, Richard Roll, and Stephen A. Ross (1986) show that macroeconomic forces are priced risk factors. These theoretical contributions imply that fluctuations in economic growth should be reflected in aggregate market performance. Accordingly, the central research problem of this study is formulated as follows: *To what extent did macroeconomic growth influence the performance and post-COVID resilience of the Moroccan stock market during the 2019–2024 period?* This problem integrates both performance (measured by MASI annual returns) and resilience (measured by recovery dynamics following the 2020 shock), within a macro-financial analytical framework. Based on the research problem and theoretical background, the study addresses the following research questions:

- **RQ1: Is there a statistically significant relationship between GDP growth and annual MASI returns during the 2019–2024 period?**
- **RQ2: Did the Moroccan stock market exhibit resilience following the COVID-19 contraction in 2020?**
- **RQ3: How do macroeconomic fluctuations contextualize the phases of contraction, rebound, correction, and stabilization observed in the post-pandemic period?**

These questions are consistent with the macro-financial linkage literature and provide a structured path toward empirical testing. Grounded in financial development theory and empirical evidence on macroeconomic determinants of stock returns (Fama, 1990; King & Levine, 1993), the study formulates the following hypothesis:

H1: GDP growth positively influences the annual return of the MASI index.

Formally:

$$\beta > 0$$

where β represents the estimated coefficient of GDP growth in the regression model. A positive and statistically significant coefficient would indicate that improvements in real economic activity are associated with higher stock market returns, supporting the theoretical proposition that financial markets reflect macroeconomic fundamentals.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative research design based on time-series analysis of annual macroeconomic and financial data over the 2019–2024 period. The objective is to examine the relationship between economic growth and stock market performance within a frontier market context. The design is explanatory in nature, as it seeks to test a theoretically grounded hypothesis derived from macro-financial linkage literature. Given the limited number of annual observations, a parsimonious econometric approach is employed to preserve statistical validity. Over-parameterization is avoided in order to maintain sufficient degrees of freedom and ensure reliable coefficient estimation. The methodological choice aligns with standard econometric principles emphasizing model simplicity when sample size is constrained (Wooldridge, 2016). The study combines two complementary analytical components:

1. Descriptive analysis, to assess the evolution of MASI returns and macroeconomic indicators during the post-COVID period.
2. Econometric estimation, to test the hypothesized relationship between GDP growth and stock market returns.

This dual structure allows for both contextual interpretation and formal hypothesis testing. The empirical analysis relies exclusively on official and institutional data to ensure reliability and transparency. Financial market indicators are obtained from the Bourse de Casablanca and the Autorité Marocaine du Marché des Capitaux (AMMC), including annual MASI index values,

market capitalization, liquidity ratios, and trading volumes. Macroeconomic data are sourced from the Haut-Commissariat au Plan (HCP), which provides official national accounts and GDP growth rates. Complementary monetary policy data, including the policy interest rate, are drawn from the Bank Al-Maghrib. When necessary, cross-verification is conducted using databases from the World Bank. The dataset covers six annual observations (2019–2024). Although limited in length, it captures the pre-pandemic benchmark year (2019), the contraction phase (2020), the rebound (2021), the inflationary correction (2022), and the stabilization period (2023–2024).

To test the research hypothesis, the following Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model is specified:

$$MASI_t = \alpha + \beta GDP_t + \varepsilon_t$$

where:

- $MASI_t$ represents the annual return of the Moroccan All Shares Index,
- GDP_t denotes the annual real GDP growth rate,
- α is the intercept term,
- β measures the sensitivity of stock returns to economic growth,
- ε_t is the error term.

The OLS estimator is selected due to its unbiasedness and efficiency under the Gauss–Markov assumptions (Greene, 2018). The parsimonious structure avoids multicollinearity concerns and preserves degrees of freedom given the small sample size. A positive and statistically significant estimate of β would support the hypothesis that economic growth positively influences stock market performance.

Table 1. Empirical analysis procedure

<i>Stage</i>	<i>Analytical component</i>	<i>Objective</i>	<i>Statistical tools</i>	<i>Expected output</i>
1	Descriptive statistics	Assess central tendency and dispersion of MASI returns and GDP growth	Mean, Standard Deviation, Minimum, Maximum	Summary statistics table highlighting volatility and variability patterns
2	Trend analysis	Identify contraction, rebound, correction, and stabilization phases	Graphical representation; Year-over-year comparison	Visual trend interpretation of market and macroeconomic evolution
3	Correlation analysis	Examine preliminary linear association between GDP growth and MASI returns	Pearson correlation coefficient	Correlation coefficient (r) and significance level
4	Regression estimation (OLS)	Test the hypothesized impact of GDP growth on MASI returns	Ordinary Least Squares estimation	Estimated coefficient (β), t-statistic, p-value, R^2

Source: Author.

V. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

The descriptive analysis provides an overview of the evolution of stock market performance and macroeconomic activity in Morocco over the 2019–2024 period. This timeframe captures four distinct phases: the pre-pandemic benchmark (2019), the COVID-19 contraction (2020), the rebound (2021), the inflationary correction (2022), and the stabilization phase (2023–2024). Examining these dynamics allows for a structured assessment of performance volatility and recovery patterns.

5.1 Evolution of MASI returns (2019–2024)

The annual returns of the MASI index reflect significant fluctuations during the study period. After a relatively stable pre-pandemic year in 2019, the market experienced a contraction of approximately -7.27% in 2020, coinciding with the severe economic shock induced by COVID-19. This decline was followed by a strong rebound in 2021, with returns reaching $+18.35\%$, indicating rapid recovery in investor confidence and expectations. However, 2022 recorded a substantial correction of -19.75% , largely associated with inflationary pressures and monetary tightening. The period 2023–2024 marked renewed stabilization, with returns of $+12.8\%$ in

2023 and +22.16% in 2024, suggesting a recovery of market valuation and improved macroeconomic outlook. The magnitude of fluctuations highlights the sensitivity of the Moroccan stock market to macroeconomic and global shocks. The rebound observed after 2020 suggests a capacity for recovery, consistent with resilience dynamics documented in crisis literature (Brunnermeier, 2009).

Figure 1. Evolution of MASI annual returns (2020–2024)

Source: Author.

5.2 Evolution of GDP growth

The trajectory of GDP growth over the same period mirrors the economic impact of the pandemic and subsequent recovery. Morocco recorded a growth rate of approximately 2.5% in 2019, followed by a sharp contraction of -7.2% in 2020, reflecting the combined effects of lockdown measures and external demand shocks.

In 2021, GDP growth surged to 7.9%, driven by economic reopening and policy support measures. The pace moderated in 2022 to 1.3%, before stabilizing at 3.4% in 2023 and 3.8% in 2024. These figures indicate a progressive normalization of economic activity.

The synchronized contraction in 2020 and rebound in 2021 suggest a close interaction between real economic activity and financial market performance.

Figure 2. Evolution of GDP growth (2019–2024)

Source: Author.

5.3 Comparative trend analysis

A comparative examination of MASI returns and GDP growth reveals notable co-movements during key phases of the period. The simultaneous contraction in 2020, followed by a strong rebound in 2021, suggests that the stock market rapidly incorporated macroeconomic recovery expectations. This pattern aligns with evidence indicating that stock markets often anticipate changes in real activity (Fama, 1990).

However, divergences appear in 2022, when stock returns declined sharply despite positive GDP growth. This discrepancy may reflect inflationary pressures and tightening monetary policy, which affected discount rates and risk perceptions independently of real output performance. The subsequent stabilization in 2023–2024 corresponds to improved macroeconomic conditions and reduced uncertainty.

Overall, the descriptive evidence indicates:

- A strong cyclical relationship between economic contraction and market downturn.
- Rapid recovery in both GDP and stock returns in 2021.
- Temporary decoupling during inflationary correction.
- Gradual normalization thereafter.

These observations provide preliminary support for the hypothesized positive relationship between economic growth and stock market performance, which will be formally tested in the regression analysis.

5.4. Correlation analysis

To assess the preliminary linear association between economic growth and stock market performance, the Pearson correlation coefficient was computed using annual data for the 2020–2024 period.

The estimated correlation coefficient is:

$$r = 0.623$$

with a p-value of:

$$p = 0.261$$

The positive correlation indicates a moderate positive association between GDP growth and MASI annual returns. This suggests that higher economic growth tends to be accompanied by improved stock market performance.

However, the relationship is not statistically significant at conventional levels ($p > 0.05$), which is expected given the very small sample size ($n = 5$). Therefore, the correlation result should be interpreted as indicative rather than conclusive.

From an economic perspective, the positive sign aligns with macro-financial theory, which posits that stock markets incorporate expectations about real economic activity (Fama, 1990).

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model estimated is:

$$MASI_t = \alpha + \beta GDP_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Table 2. Estimated results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value
Intercept	1.564	7.745	0.202	0.853
GDP Growth	2.008	1.454	1.381	0.261

Source: Author

Model statistics

- $R^2 = 0.389$
- Adjusted $R^2 = 0.185$
- F-statistic p-value = 0.261
- Durbin–Watson = 1.913
- The estimated coefficient for GDP growth ($\beta = 2.008$) is positive, indicating that a one-percentage-point increase in GDP growth is associated with an approximate 2-percentage-point increase in MASI returns.
- The R^2 value (0.389) suggests that approximately 39% of the variation in stock market returns over the period can be explained by changes in economic growth.

- Although the coefficient is not statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.261$), the positive sign is consistent with theoretical expectations and previous empirical findings (Chen et al., 1986; Fama, 1990).
- Given the small sample size, statistical inference remains limited. The emphasis should therefore be placed on the **directional consistency and economic interpretation** rather than strict hypothesis rejection.

Market resilience refers to the ability of a financial system to absorb shocks, recover, and return to a stable growth trajectory (Brunnermeier, 2009).

The Moroccan stock market exhibited four distinct phases during the study period:

1. Shock phase (2020)

- GDP growth: -7.2%
- MASI return: -7.27%

The synchronous contraction indicates a strong transmission of macroeconomic shock to financial markets.

2. Rebound phase (2021)

- GDP growth: 7.9%
- MASI return: 18.35%

The rapid recovery in both economic activity and stock returns suggests adaptive market behavior and restored investor confidence.

3. Correction phase (2022)

- GDP growth: 1.3%
- MASI return: -19.75%

The divergence between positive GDP growth and negative stock returns likely reflects inflationary pressures and monetary tightening rather than pure output dynamics.

4. Stabilization phase (2023–2024)

- GDP growth stabilizes around $3\text{--}4\%$
- MASI returns return to double-digit positive levels

This phase indicates normalization and renewed growth expectations.

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimator relies on the Gauss–Markov theorem, which states that under certain assumptions, OLS provides the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE) (Wooldridge, 2016; Greene, 2018). These assumptions include:

1. **Linearity in parameters**

The model is linear in coefficients, which is satisfied:

$$MASI_t = \alpha + \beta GDP_t + \varepsilon_t$$

2. **Random sampling**

Although the dataset consists of annual macroeconomic observations rather than cross-sectional sampling, the time-series framework assumes observations are generated by a stable data-generating process.

3. **No perfect multicollinearity**

With only one explanatory variable, multicollinearity is not an issue.

4. **Zero conditional mean**

$$E(\varepsilon_t | GDP_t) = 0$$

This assumption implies that omitted variables are not systematically correlated with GDP growth. In practice, this condition may be restrictive, as inflation and interest rates could influence both GDP and stock returns.

5. **Homoskedasticity**

The variance of the error term is assumed constant:

$$Var(\varepsilon_t | GDP_t) = \sigma^2$$

With $n = 5$ effective observations (2020–2024), formal heteroskedasticity testing lacks statistical power.

Under these assumptions, the OLS estimator is unbiased and efficient within the class of linear estimators. The principal methodological constraint of this study is the limited number of annual observations. With only five effective data points in the regression:

- Degrees of freedom = 3
- Statistical power is low
- Confidence intervals are wide
- Hypothesis testing is sensitive to minor data variations

As emphasized by Wooldridge (2016), small samples increase estimator variance and reduce the reliability of t-statistics. Consequently, the non-significant p-value (0.261) should not be interpreted as definitive evidence of no relationship, but rather as an indication of limited inferential strength.

The estimated R^2 (0.389) indicates that approximately 39% of the variation in MASI returns is explained by GDP growth. While moderate, this explanatory power is economically meaningful given the simplicity of the model. In macro-financial regressions with aggregate data, R^2 values

are often limited due to the influence of global shocks and investor sentiment (Campbell, Lo, & MacKinlay, 1997). Therefore, the economic magnitude of the coefficient ($\beta = 2.008$) is more informative than strict statistical significance. A 1% increase in GDP growth being associated with a 2% increase in stock returns suggests substantial macroeconomic sensitivity, consistent with the Arbitrage Pricing Theory framework (Ross, 1976).

VI. DISCUSSION

The empirical findings provide economically meaningful—though statistically constrained—evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and stock market performance in Morocco during the post-COVID period. The positive coefficient obtained in the regression model suggests that improvements in real economic activity are associated with higher MASI returns, which is consistent with macro-financial linkage theory and multifactor asset pricing frameworks (Chen et al., 1986; Fama, 1990). The synchronized contraction in 2020 and rebound in 2021 further reinforce the view that the Casablanca Stock Exchange incorporates macroeconomic information into prices. This behavior aligns with the semi-strong form of market efficiency, according to which publicly available macroeconomic signals are reflected in stock valuations (Fama, 1970). However, the divergence observed in 2022—when stock returns declined despite positive GDP growth—highlights the role of additional systematic factors, notably inflationary pressures and monetary tightening, which may affect discount rates independently of output dynamics.

From a structural perspective, the results suggest that the Moroccan stock market exhibits cyclical resilience rather than structural insulation from shocks. The rapid recovery following the 2020 contraction indicates adaptive market behavior and restored investor confidence, yet the sensitivity to macroeconomic volatility underscores the limited depth and diversification typical of frontier markets. The moderate R^2 obtained in the regression implies that economic growth explains a substantial portion of return variability, but not all of it, leaving room for global factors, investor sentiment, and monetary conditions to influence performance (Campbell, Lo, & MacKinlay, 1997). Given the small sample size, conclusions must remain cautious; nevertheless, the directional consistency of the findings supports the hypothesis that real economic recovery played a central role in the post-pandemic rebound of the Moroccan equity market.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study examined the post-COVID performance and resilience of the Casablanca Stock Exchange over the 2019–2024 period, with a particular focus on the relationship between economic growth and stock market returns. The descriptive analysis identified four distinct phases: the pandemic shock (2020), the strong rebound (2021), the inflation-driven correction (2022), and the stabilization phase (2023–2024). The empirical results indicate a positive association between GDP growth and MASI annual returns. Although the estimated coefficient is not statistically significant at conventional levels due to the limited sample size, its positive sign and economic magnitude are consistent with macro-financial theory and prior empirical findings (Fama, 1990; Chen et al., 1986). Approximately 39% of the variation in stock returns during the period can be explained by changes in economic growth, suggesting that real economic activity played a meaningful role in shaping market dynamics.

From a structural standpoint, the Moroccan stock market demonstrated cyclical resilience by recovering rapidly after the 2020 contraction. However, the sharp correction observed in 2022 underscores the market's sensitivity to inflationary pressures and monetary tightening. These findings suggest that while the Moroccan capital market is capable of absorbing shocks and rebounding in favorable macroeconomic conditions, it remains exposed to external and domestic macroeconomic volatility. Methodologically, the study is constrained by the small number of annual observations, which limits statistical inference and calls for cautious interpretation. Future research based on quarterly data or longer time series would allow for more robust econometric testing, including dynamic modeling and causality analysis. Overall, the results contribute to the limited empirical literature on frontier markets and provide insight into the macroeconomic determinants of stock market performance in the Moroccan context.

REFERENCES

- Al-Awadhi, A. M., Alsaifi, K., Al-Awadhi, A., & Alhammadi, S. (2020). Death and contagious infectious diseases: Impact of the COVID-19 virus on stock market returns. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 27, 100326.
- Ashraf, B. N. (2020). Stock markets' reaction to COVID-19: Cases or fatalities? *Research in International Business and Finance*, 54, 101249.
- Brunnermeier, M. K. (2009). Deciphering the liquidity and credit crunch 2007–2008. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 23(1), 77–100.
- Campbell, J. Y. (1991). A variance decomposition for stock returns. *Economic Journal*, 101(405), 157–179.
- Campbell, J. Y., & Shiller, R. J. (1988). The dividend-price ratio and expectations of future dividends and discount factors. *Review of Financial Studies*, 1(3), 195–228.
- Campbell, J. Y., Lo, A. W., & MacKinlay, A. C. (1997). *The econometrics of financial markets*. Princeton University Press.
- Chen, N.-F., Roll, R., & Ross, S. A. (1986). Economic forces and the stock market. *Journal of Business*, 59(3), 383–403.
- Didier, T., Huneus, F., Larrain, M., & Schmukler, S. L. (2021). Financing firms in hibernation during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 53, 100837.
- Fama, E. F. (1970). Efficient capital markets: A review of theory and empirical work. *Journal of Finance*, 25(2), 383–417.
- Fama, E. F. (1990). Stock returns, expected returns, and real activity. *Journal of Finance*, 45(4), 1089–1108.
- Fama, E. F. (1991). Efficient capital markets: II. *Journal of Finance*, 46(5), 1575–1617.
- Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (1992). The cross-section of expected stock returns. *Journal of Finance*, 47(2), 427–465.
- Fama, E. F., & Schwert, G. W. (1977). Asset returns and inflation. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 5(2), 115–146.
- Fisher, I. (1930). *The theory of interest*. Macmillan.
- Geske, R., & Roll, R. (1983). The fiscal and monetary linkage between stock returns and inflation. *Journal of Finance*, 38(1), 1–33.
- Greene, W. H. (2018). *Econometric analysis* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- International Monetary Fund. (2020). *World economic outlook, April 2020: The great lockdown*. IMF.

- Kendall, M. G. (1953). The analysis of economic time-series—Part I: Prices. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series A (General)*, 116(1), 11–34.
- King, R. G., & Levine, R. (1993). Finance and growth: Schumpeter might be right. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 108(3), 717–737.
- Levine, R. (1997). Financial development and economic growth: Views and agenda. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 35(2), 688–726.
- Lintner, J. (1965). The valuation of risk assets and the selection of risky investments in stock portfolios and capital budgets. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 47(1), 13–37.
- Lo, A. W. (2004). The adaptive markets hypothesis: Market efficiency from an evolutionary perspective. *Journal of Portfolio Management*, 30(5), 15–29.
- Lo, A. W., & MacKinlay, A. C. (1988). Stock market prices do not follow random walks: Evidence from a simple specification test. *Review of Financial Studies*, 1(1), 41–66.
- Markowitz, H. (1952). Portfolio selection. *Journal of Finance*, 7(1), 77–91.
- Modigliani, F., & Miller, M. H. (1958). The cost of capital, corporation finance and the theory of investment. *American Economic Review*, 48(3), 261–297.
- Mossin, J. (1966). Equilibrium in a capital asset market. *Econometrica*, 34(4), 768–783.
- Ross, S. A. (1976). The arbitrage theory of capital asset pricing. *Journal of Economic Theory*, 13(3), 341–360.
- Samuelson, P. A. (1965). Proof that properly anticipated prices fluctuate randomly. *Industrial Management Review*, 6(2), 41–49.
- Sharpe, W. F. (1964). Capital asset prices: A theory of market equilibrium under conditions of risk. *Journal of Finance*, 19(3), 425–442.
- Shiller, R. J. (2003). From efficient markets theory to behavioral finance. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 17(1), 83–104.
- Tobin, J. (1958). Liquidity preference as behavior toward risk. *Review of Economic Studies*, 25(2), 65–86.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2016). *Introductory econometrics: A modern approach* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Zaremba, A., Kizys, R., Aharon, D. Y., & Demir, E. (2020). Infected markets: Novel coronavirus, government interventions, and stock return volatility around the globe. *Finance Research Letters*, 35, 101597.